

Unconventional wisdom: Recognizing *anamnesis* in all phases of worship
(Communication Studies)

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Abstract

At a moment in which the evangelical Christian community in the United States has reached a turning point in message and method of communication, I propose that all Christian activity be understood as anamnesis, that the entire Christian faith be conceived as collective memory.

But the Comforter, which is the Holy Ghost, whom the Father will send in my name, he shall teach you all things, and bring all things to your remembrance, whatsoever I have said unto you. (John 14:26, KJV)

For where two or three are gathered together in my name, there am I in the midst of them. (Matthew 18:20, KJV)

Until evangelical Christian churches in the United States¹ change their orientation to communication, rocky times are in store. Recent research indicates that in fifteen years, the percentage of Americans who do not belong to a Christian church has risen from a fourth to a third of the population (Kinnaman & Lyons, 2007). People report that they choose not to belong to a church because they believe churches are too tied to politics, too angry, too unconcerned with problems that seem urgent and salient. Gabe Lyons, one of the report's authors explains, "I think the church has tried to give very simple answers to very complex issues" (Flynn, 2007, p. F4).

The mismatch between issue and answer is just the tip of the iceberg of larger change. As the political landscape undergoes catastrophic rearrangement, many report that the role of evangelical Christianity in public life is similarly moving through a reconstruction of revolutionary scale. As Rick Warren replaces Jerry Falwell and Billy Graham as its public face (Kirkpatrick, 2007), the foundational assumptions within which evangelical Christians speak to one another and to the world are open to question. All three are powerful communicators, but Warren's approach to communication, ranging from topics to organizational structure, is so different as to be nearly unrecognizable. And such radical change may be just what is needed, to turn us away from struggling with the world and toward struggling with our core teachings. Lyons concludes,

¹ Much of what I assert in this paper is likely applicable to Christian churches of every tradition and in every country. But in the earliest stages of this research, I limit my claims to evangelical Christianity in the United States.

The surprise was that they had been up close and personal with the Christian faith and walked away with these reactions. It deepened the need for us as Christians to not be in denial, but to own it and accept the real substantive issues they are pointing to in their critique and to become more like Jesus in our perspective and behaviors (Flynn, 2007, p. F4).

In the sections that follow, I begin with past definitions of what a Christian church *is*, and then highlight past work that defines and describes the role of *anamnesis* in liturgy. I then juxtapose that idea with communication scholarship into the phenomenon of collective memory, and examine several different modes of church activity for their anamnestic function, their role in generating the church's identity through group activity that reinforces the church's constitutive event.

Collective memory and *anamnesis*

If a dominant communicative purpose, or mode, exists for the body of evangelical Christian churches, then it ought to be evident in that body's essence. Wilken (1995) pinpoints the church as "a living community that is the bearer of ancient traditions received from those who have gone before" (p. 168). Signier concurs that the Christian community is "bound by rituals of commemoration" (2001, p. ix). But these traits could be identified in nearly any faith tradition. Bradbury sets Christianity apart from other religions in general, and Judaism particular, arguing that Christianity's distinct purpose "lies precisely in the fact that it is called to join individuals from all peoples, not one particular people. The heart of this vocation lies in the Christ event, and it is the life, teachings, cross and resurrection of Jesus which form the foundational memory which the Church identifies" (2004, p. 34). The communicative contour,

then, is not from one to many, but *from many to many*, in the circulating economy of community.

Bradbury's remark establishes not only that Christian churches have important business to do with multitudes, but also that the kernel of their message is the contemporary salience of a past happening, the "Christ event." Kilmartin elaborates:

The movement is not from the historical event of the cross to us; the event is not withdrawn from its historical context and made to come to us. Rather, we go to the event, are made present to it. The movement by which we meet a "passed" event is called memory. It is by remembrance that we meet the sacrifice of the cross (1994, p. 450).

The *memory* of the cross, then, is the lifeblood of Christian communities and community. Signier argues that this memory is the "province of the Synagogue and the Church and thus provides a corporate identity fixed in the relationship with the transcendent" (p. x). If Christian churches work out a communal identity that is continually generated and renewed through expression of memory, then the dominant communicative mode of the Christian church has found its niche in the repertoire of communicative frameworks: collective memory.

The concept of collective memory originated with Maurice Halbwachs (1992), who argued in a most literal and non-metaphorical sense that individuals removed from contact with other human beings would be unable to form memories. In Halbwachs' account, similar to Mead's explanation of the self as an accretion of feedback from other selves, the individual grasps the *meaning* of events by measuring them against others' messages about those events. He insisted that this process of coding experience into the comprehensible is necessarily a group enterprise. Other scholars inside and out of the communication studies field have elaborated on the idea at length. LaCapra (1999) describes collective memory as the value-laden understanding

of history that gives valence to the evidence gathered and interpreted by historians. If history is the data, then collective memory provides claim and warrant. In a condensing metaphor well-suited to leaders of worship services, Winter & Sivan (1999) compare the communal process of establishing frames of collective memory to “a sort of choir singing, or better still, a sing-along” (p. 28). Stepnisky (2005) cautions against mistaking past events that are merely powerful or evocative for collective memories; he insists that collective memories have an *applied* aspect, that they are “not simply the representation of an event but also a way of seeing and living in relation to a variety of significant, sacred events as they have been constituted through shared stories” (p. 1387). Finally, Hasian (2005) calls on communication scholars to move beyond simply *identifying* collective memories, or tracing their provenance, to a more demanding commitment to

...offer informed judgments about the consequential impact of believing in certain rhetorical figurations. . . . As critics of public memories, we need to be reflexive as we study public deliberations that are influenced by the ways that various communities think about the meaning of traumatic experience, vicarious memories, or historical transference (p. 233).

The search for traces of collective memory by observers of Christian churches has, thus far, been extremely limited. A number of authors² have applied the concept of collective memory to the nation of Israel, perhaps drawn by the rich cache of commands to remember throughout the Old Testament, such as Exodus 12:14’s directions concerning the perpetual celebration of Passover: “And this day shall be unto you for a memorial; and ye shall keep it a feast to the LORD throughout your generations; ye shall keep it a feast by an ordinance for ever” (KJV). Answering Pope Benedict XVI’s call to re-establish Christianity as the “religion according to

² See e.g. Smith, 2002; Yadin, 2004.

reason” (Ratzinger, 2005), Wilken urges contemporary Christians to attend to words laid down by their ancestors, both within and outside of the canon, arguing that

Without memory, our intellectual life is impoverished, barren, ephemeral, subject to the whims of the moment.... there can be no Christian intellectual life without reference to the writings of the prophets and evangelists, the doctrines of the church fathers, the conceptual niceties of the scholastics, the language of the liturgy, the songs of the poets and hymn writers, the exploits of the martyrs, and the holy tales of the saints (pp. 179-180).

Signier isolates a uniquely American demographic trend that adds extra piquancy to the urgency of bolstering memory in Christian churches: “because of the enormous geographic and economic mobility of Americans. Precisely because they have left their past behind, they are in need of collective identity and memory which will help them develop a set of stories and rituals to transmit values and identity to the next generation” (pp. xi-xii).

But it is in exploration of the liturgical practice of communion that this idea has found its fullest expression. The twenty-second chapter of Luke places Christ at a Passover seder (vv. 7-8), the Old Testament celebration of memory, instructing the apostles, “this do in remembrance of me” (v. 19, KJV). The word ἀναμνησιν, *anamnēsis*, has lent its name to the task in worship services of obeying Christ’s command by reenacting, with various degrees of asserted immediacy, the breaking of bread and pouring of wine as tokens of the arrival of the new covenant (Bradshaw, 2001). The controversy over its mystical significance, over how literally the communion summons the foodstuffs used in an act thousands of years in the past, was one of the key motivating forces that propelled the earliest denominations apart in the Protestant reformation. Silberling explains,

... Luther rejected the Catholic doctrine of transubstantiation, the presence of “Christ” in the eucharist, in favor of the idea that mystical union with “Christ” only occurs at the moment of the liturgical act but does not continue afterward. Zwingli, on the other hand, argued that the eucharist was merely a symbolic act of bringing to memory past events with no notion of any sense of cultic participation. Calvin attempted to moderate between Luther’s notion of sharing in Christ’s omnipresent body and Zwingli’s symbol by arguing that Messiah’s saving power, not his body and blood, was what was present in the elements themselves (p. 5).

Bradbury sidesteps these divisions by distributing the anamnestic function to other set pieces in a worship service. Borrowing Wilken’s insight that “Language is a vehicle of memory” (p. 179), Bradbury lays a foundation for his challenge to conventional commemorative worship with the observation that “Our concern is the means by which memory mediates the reality of covenant within the process of the formation of the identity of the Church” (p. 13). Following the force of this reasoning, Bradbury throws down a gauntlet for reimagining the mnemonic impulse in worship in innovative ways, and it is his proposal that is the jumping off point for what follows:

We normally retain the word anamnesis solely for what is going on in one particular part of the Lord’s Supper: however, what is happening in preaching can also be considered an anamnestic practice. We have already noted the idea that the Church exists within a society made up of competing collective memories which are becoming increasingly fragmented. In preaching, the scriptural text which forms the foundation of the sermon is brought to mind, or perhaps, brought to life. This then, provides one particular collective

memory through which the competing collective memories of a fragmented society can be approached. (pp. 35-36)

I wholeheartedly endorse Bradbury's suggestion that preaching is anamnestic. However, I believe, and it is the purpose of the remainder of this paper to argue, that he did not go far enough. Christ promised, in a verse which is one of this paper's epigraphs, that the Holy Spirit would be our memory, and that He would be among us every time we gathered. The anamnestic essence that Bradbury recognizes in preaching is present in many other devotional activities as well, and once we recognize it, we may arrive at a different and better understanding of worship.

Diversifying and distributing the anamnestic function

Many standard practices that are unrelated to communion are integrally bound up with the perpetuation of teaching against the danger of forgetting, and the group generation of memory as an engine of identity creation. Some are specific to particular denominations, while others are widely practiced, although often in different ways.

Participatory corporate worship. The Religious Society of Friends' tradition of unprogrammed worship is non-hierarchical and unplanned, inviting members of the meeting to speak as they feel the leading of the Spirit (Cooper, 1990). In such worship gatherings, the assembly experience their place in the church as participation, as experience, rather than as passive audience. The teaching and identity are continuous; the substance of the teaching is worked out in the decision to speak, in discernment of the message's source, in selecting words, in listening carefully to others, and in listening to the silence.

Fellowship. Planned activity in churches of any denomination that follows the instruction of Hebrews 10:24-25, "And let us consider one another to provoke unto love and to good works: Not forsaking the assembling of ourselves together, as the manner of some is; but exhorting one

another” (KJV) is an occasion for workshopping of the congregation’s group identity through the terministic screen of Christian teachings. Where people work, play, celebrate, or otherwise behave collaboratively against a purpose or context that renews their allegiance to the risen Christ, their resolve to live out the Christ event, they are staving off forgetfulness and renewing Christ’s constitutive words and actions.

Daily walk. Following the descriptions of Enoch in Genesis 5 and Noah in Genesis 6, as well as Christ’s instruction in Luke 9:23 that His disciple must “take up his cross daily, and follow me” (KJV), many teachers from many denominations teach that an emphasis of Christian discipline must be the cultivation of the daily walk (Hayford, 2000; Polich 2005). The daily walk is an explicit turn against forgetfulness, as it consists of a commitment to carry out acts of devotion to God in every phase of daily life, including the workplace, social gatherings, daily travel time, household errands, and even morning and evening grooming. One antecedent of this discipline that makes explicit reference to the necessity of aggressively combating the danger of forgetfulness is found in James 1:23-25:

For if any be a hearer of the word, and not a doer, he is like unto a man beholding his natural face in a glass: For he beholdeth himself, and goeth his way, and straightway forgetteth what manner of man he was. But whoso looketh into the perfect law of liberty, and continueth therein, he being not a forgetful hearer, but a doer of the work, this man shall be blessed in his deed (KJV).

Prayer. In many Christian denominations, there exists a frequent practice of corporate prayer, including such variants as group silent prayer, group whispered prayer, prayer led by a recognized church leader, prayer led by any member of the church, and prayer begun by one person and then continued by others in brief prayer fragments. Uniting all these practices, “the

central element is that corporate prayer is, by definition, prayer where the agent is not us individually but us as a praying community...corporate prayer is the form we need to create and re-create our identity as a people, for *leiturgia* is at root ‘the people at prayer’” (Harris, 1989, p. 98).

Communion is reenactment, or imitation, as a focused and deliberate move to obey Christ’s command. But obedience to that command comes in other activities as well. On every occasion in which we gather and constitute ourselves as a body under the new covenant He announced at the Last Supper, we reinscribe that memory and reject forgetfulness. All of these practices complement written and spoken teachings with a more robust stream of sensory data, to backstop explicit memory with implicit, semantic memory with episodic (Baddeley, 1999). When Christian gatherings include worship, fellowship, study and labor that is experiential, that brings together church members in activity, then elements of memory which code and retain behavior are enlisted in the anamnestic function; we remember what we *do* along with what we hear, as James explained.

Collective memory as a unified theory of Christianity

In 1984, Walter Fisher’s proposal that humans were *homo narrans*, and that all communication could be understood as narrative in nature, challenged many communication scholars to re-examine their starting assumptions. One year later, Fisher noted with apparent pleasure the vigorous discussion he had spurred, and emphasized that his claims were not *inconsistent* with other frameworks for understanding communication, but that all of them were “an episode in the story of life” (1985, p. 347). In particular instances, specialized forms of communication may have emerged to fulfill certain needed functions, but in a *larger* sense they were all elements of human experience which could be most fully understood as story.

Here, drawing from the previous sections, I propose that all Christian activity, all of Christian life, is anamnestic. Collective memory is a unified theory of the Christian church. The twelfth chapter of the books of Romans and First Corinthians both develop the claim that the church can *only* be understood as an interdependent assemblage, that it has identity, that it is, indeed, a “body,” that is constituted by its believers operating as a living, acting entity. That, joined with the central importance of passionate assent, remembrance, and a fusion of understanding with behavior, provides the basis for viewing Christianity as nothing less, and nothing more, than collective memory of the Christ event.

Beyond simply observing that memories are built in collaboration with others, collective memory scholars have devoted substantial attention to the work of *framing* memories, and the struggle that takes place between divergent framing approaches toward the goal of establishing one as the dominant frame (Irwin-Zarecka, 1994). The distinct practices that separate denominations may thus be accommodated under the collective memory framework as different frames. The relative dominance of various frames may be less than clear, as membership swings are determined by a complex tangle of root causes, but just as founding events in other communities can be understood differently by different members, and the dialogue and disputes over such interpretations can add substance and insight to the shared identity, so denominational distinctives may actually serve as opportunities, as sites of examination and critical reflection that challenge believers to live their beliefs, to learn their beliefs, and, most importantly, *to make the living and learning one mode of obedience to the Almighty*, continuous, undivided, whole.

Viewing all worship as anamnestic, all Christianity as collective memory, does not provide an easy answer to the difficulties that evangelical Christian churches currently experience in attracting those who want to participate in the faith, but have negative impressions

of the experience of church life. It does not point to a clear, smooth path away from political entanglements. It does, however, make clear the church's core function, and perhaps make *more* clear the deserved lower-priority status of such battles, whether temporal or internecine. Perhaps it is simply that a moment presents itself in which the past approaches to communication, among believers and between believers and non-believers, will no longer do. The status quo is not tenable. If the appropriation of lived and enacted memory to a few demarcated ceremonial exercises has compartmentalized it and checked its transformative and identity-clarifying power, then a changed understanding may offer an opportunity to challenge previous negative experiences, to write them *out* of individuals' memories and replace them with a transformed church that can set about the task of cultivating *new* memories of oneness and inclusion in the evangelical Christian church's mission.

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